

Analysis of Murabahah Financing Marketing Strategy at PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita, Medan, North Sumatra, Indonesia

Andri Setiawan, Endang Sulistya Rini, Isfenti Sadalia & Muhamad Toyib Daulay

Abstract:

Financial institutions are one of the factors driving the economic growth of a country; they play an essential and indispensable role. One of the Islamic banking financial institutions, whose operational pattern follows the principles of sharia or Muamalah Islam, is that the BPRS has two main functions, namely the fund collection function and the financing function. The purpose of this study is to analyze one of the strategies that can support the BPRS to carry out its functions, namely the marketing mix strategy (product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence on interests and decisions using Murabahah Financing in PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita. Financing is the provision of funds or receipts in the form of profit sharing transactions in the form of Mudharabah and musyarakah, lease transactions in ijarah muntahiya bittamlik, sale and purchase transactions in the form of murabahah receivables, loan transactions in the form of qardh receivables, and leasing transactions in the form of ijarah for multilateral transactions based on agreement between sharia banks and other parties requiring the party financed or funded by the fund to recover the funds after a certain period of time in exchange for ujah, without compensation or profit sharing. The sample in this study is PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan totaling 168 customers. The research was conducted at the location of PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita. The results showed that the most influential variables on interest and the decision to propose Murabahah financing were product variables. While the variables with low effects are price and process. The strategy that needs to be done to increase further interest and the decision to propose Murabahah financing is to improve prices and the marketing process.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Intention to Apply, Decision, Murabahah, Financing

IJSB

Accepted 12 February 2019
Published 17 February 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2567414

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INTRODUCTION

Sharia banking institutions in Indonesia have shown tremendous growth over the past few years. That fact is due to a large number of people who want banking that is free of luck, although previously sharia banking had experienced periods of crisis, it could be saved. Besides as an intermediary institution, the function of Islamic banking institutions is also an investment institution that has a role in supporting the economic growth of a nation. Also, the role of sharia banking is also the support of business decisions that become the people's needs for economic activity. One of the sharia banking financial institutions whose operational patterns are by Islamic principles or Muamalah Islam is BPRS. The institute has two main functions such as funding and financing. Sharia BPRs can be interpreted as financial institutions as conventional Micro Banking (BPR), whose operations use shariah principles, especially revenue sharing. The purpose of BPRS is to serve people who are unable to access modern banking services. BPRS should continue to be well maintained in competing with commercial banks, particularly in the microfinance segment. Nevertheless, performance measurement and solutions are not similar to other commercial banks because, in some regions, BPRS have a character in providing solutions, and relatively different amongst BPRS. Therefore, BPRS Amanah Insan Cita should have a superior marketing strategy with other BPRS or commercial banks.

Marketing strategy is a series of goals and objectives, policies and rules that lead to enterprise marketing efforts from time to time at each level and its reference and allocation primarily as a company's response to the changing environment and the state of competition (Assauri, 2013). The marketing mix is a collection of marketing variables that are controlled and used by a business entity to achieve marketing goals in the target market. The marketing mix is a mix of marketing activities to maximize combinations to bring the most satisfying results. The marketing mix strategy that is well designed will influence the buyer's decision to buy (Alma, 2011). While purchase decisions are the process of determining consumer choices from the various alternative options available to the product that best suits the desired needs. Financing is the provision of funds or equivalent claims in the form of profit sharing transactions in the form of Mudharabah and Musyarakah, rental transactions in the form of ijarah muntahiya bittamlik, sales transactions in the form of Murabahah receivables, borrowing transactions borrowing in the form of qardh receivables, and lease transactions services in the form of ijarah for multiyasa transactions based on the approval or agreement between the sharia banks and other parties requiring the party financed or funded by the fund to recover the fund after a certain period of time at the expense of ujarah, without compensation or profit sharing. Concerning the problem above some queries that need to be solved the solution is:

1. Does marketing mix strategy consisting of product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence influence the decision to use Murabahah financing in BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan?
2. How could marketing strategies improve the decision on Murabahah financing at BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Product

Products are goods or services designed in such a way as to the purpose of marketing. Lupiyoadi, in Suti (2010) is a whole product concept or process that provides some valuable benefits to consumers. The product classification can be of different kinds of viewpoints.

Based on tangible or not, products are classified into two primary groups, among them are goods and services (Tjiptono, 2008). Goods are products that are physical, can be seen, touched, felt, held, stored, transferred, and in other physical treatments. In terms of durability, there are two kinds of goods: nondurable and durable goods. Nondurable Goods are tangible goods that are usually consumed in one or more times, and Durable Goods is a durable tangible item with an economic age for normal use is one year or more. Services are activities, benefits or satisfaction offered for sale — for example, a repair shop, beauty salon, skinny, hotel, educational institution, and more. In addition to its durability, products are generally also classified based on who their customers are and for what products they consume. Based on these criteria, products can be differentiated into consumer's goods and industrial goods. Consumer goods are goods consumed for the benefit of the end consumer themselves (individuals and households), it does not serve the purpose of business. Generally, consumer goods can be classified into four types, namely convenience goods, shopping goods, specialty goods, and unsought goods: Convenience goods are items that generally have a high purchasing frequency, needed in a short time, and require only minimal effort in comparison and purchase — examples: rice, oil, soap, toothpaste, etc. Shopping goods are goods that are in the process of selection and purchase compared to consumers among the various alternatives available — examples: household appliances, clothing, and furniture. Specialty goods are items that have unique brand identifiers or identities where a group of consumers is willing to make a special effort to buy them. Generally, a special kind of specialty items comprises of luxury items with specific brands and models, such as Lamborgini cars, fashion designs such as Christian Dior and Versace. Unsought Goods are items unknown to consumers or if they are known, but generally have not been thought to buy them. Industrial goods are goods consumed by industrialists for purposes other than consumption directly, namely: to be changed, and it is manufactured into another item then by the manufacturer, for reseller without physical transformation

Price

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2013), a sum of money is charged to an item or service or the amount of money the consumer exchanged for the benefit of owning or using the product or service. Pricing has a significant role in the buyer's decision-making process (Tjiptono, 2008), namely: the role of allocation of the price that is the price function in helping the buyers to decide on the highest benefit or utilities based on their purchasing power. The role of information and price is the price function in capturing consumers about product factors, such as quality. It is helpful in a buyer's situation to have difficulty assessing the product's factors or its benefits objectively. The most common perception is that high prices reflect high quality.

Place

According to Heizer & Render (2015), the location is a cost driver and revenue, and the location often has the power to make the company's business strategy. Strategic locations aim to maximize profits from new company locations. According to Kotler (2008), one of the keys to success is location, and the location begins with selecting the community. Decisions depend on the potential of economic growth and stability, competition, political climate, and others. Before a company builds a factory, it is planned as best as possible because the location affects the operating or production costs, selling prices, and the ability of the company to compete in the market (Subagy, 2000).

Promotion

Promotion would help companies in communicating with consumers. Promotions are delivered in the form of information about the products offered. Kotler and Armstrong (2014) define the definition of promotion refers to activities that communicate to merits of the product and persuade target customers to buy it. Lupiyoadi (2013) defines the definition of promotion as a corporate activity to communicate the benefits of the product and as a tool to influence consumers in the purchasing or use of services as needed. Promotion according to Stanton in Alma (2013) The definition of promotion is an exercise in information, persuasion and conversely, a person who is persuaded is also being informed. Based on the definition above the promotion is an attempt to notify or offer products or services on purpose by attracting prospective consumers to buy or consume. With the promotion of producers or distributors expecting a rise in sales.

People

People are actors who play an influential role in serving the services so that it can affect buyer perceptions. Elements of people are employees of companies, consumers, and other consumers. Attitudes and actions of employees, dressing, and appearance influence the success of service delivery.

Process

The process is the actual procedure, mechanism, and flow of activity used to deliver the services. Process elements have the meaning of delivering services. Service process is a principal factor in the marketing mix of services such as customer service will be pleased to feel the service delivery system as part of the service itself. Based on the explanation of the marketing mix, it can be concluded that the marketing mix has elements that are very influential in sales because the element can affect the interest consumers in purchasing decisions.

Physical Evidence

The physical environment is a real thing that affects consumer decisions to buy and consume or services offered. Elements included in the physical environment include environment or physical building, equipment, fixtures, logos, colors, and other items.

Customer Decision

Decisions are something that consumers decide to make choices for the purchase of goods or services. The decision is a choice of two or more possibilities. Decisions are in two categories: programmed and not programmed. Decisions are also interpreted as the problem-solving process that originates from the background of the problem, identifying the problem until a conclusion or recommendation is made. Recommendations are used as a guide for decision making. The customer's decision to decide on the purchase of goods or services after going through the process is the introduction of needs, information seeking, and evaluating the alternatives that led to the decision of the customer's decision to take the loan (Fahmi, 2013). Steps in the Purchase Decision Process. Purchase decisions relate to activities where a consumer will decide to search for a product or service he or she wants. This desire begins with the urgent need for the consumer. Several patterns of behavior determine when to make a purchase. The stage is as follows: an introduction to Problems / Needs. This case is the buying process begins when the buyer is aware of a problem or need. The buyer feels the difference between the actual situation and the situation he wants. Search Information.

Information search begins when consumers see that demand can be fulfilled by buying a product. Consumers will search for information stored in their internal memory search or from external search. External search is the process of seeking information on various products and brands, purchases or consumption to the consumer environment. For example, through friends, neighbors, advertisers, salespeople, packaging, marketing personnel, mass media, etc. Alternative Evaluation. At this stage, consumers evaluate price and brand options with the expected benefits and narrow the selection to the chosen alternative. Consumers look at each product as a set of attributes with varying capabilities in delivering the merits and satisfying needs. The attributes that appeal to buyers vary by product: Camera: image sharpness, camera speed, camera size, price; Hotel: Location, cleanliness, atmosphere, cost. Purchase Decision. In the evaluation stage, consumers form a preference among brands in the selected group. Consumers may also form buying interests to buy the most preferred brands — post-purchase Behavior. Post purchasing the product, consumers will feel a certain level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Consumers will also take the purchase action and use the product. (Thamrin and Tantri, 2012),

Key factors that affect buying behavior

Factors that influence purchase behavior include culture, social, personal and psychological factors. Cultural factors have the most widespread and deep influence on consumer behavior. Culture consists of cultures, subcultures (including nationalities, religions, racial groups, and geographic areas), and social classes. Culture is the determination of the most basic desires and behavior. Growing children get a set of values and behaviors from families and other institutions. Social factor, consumer behavior is also influenced by social factors such as reference group, family, and the role and social status. A group of referrals consists of all groups having direct influence (face to face) or indirect effects on one's attitude or behavior, such as family, friends, neighbors, and co-workers. Personal factors A buyer's decision is also influenced by the personal characteristics of the buyer's life and the stage of life cycle, occupation, economic condition (income, savings and wealth, debt, interest, and ability to borrow), lifestyle and personality and buyer's self-concept. Psychological factors. People's purchasing options are also influenced by motivation, perception, knowledge, and beliefs and attitudes. Motivation: the need comes from a psychological state associated with tensions such as thirst, hunger, dislikes or the need for recognition, appreciation, or sense of ownership. A need will change into a motive if the need has reached a certain level. Perception: motivated people will act affected by their perceptions of certain situations. As a process in which individuals choose, formulate, and interpret information inputs to create a meaningful picture of the world. Entry information is received through sight, feeling, hearing, smell, and touch. When we look at the building, feel cold, hear sales information and advertising, smell the air, meaning we receive information. Confidence and attitude: through acting and learning, people gain confidence and attitude. These two factors then affect their purchasing behavior. From the concepts and theories described in the previous chapter, the authors proposed the hypotheses in this study as follows:

H1 = The effect of marketing mix strategy on decision making using Murabahah financing in BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan

H2 = The effect of marketing strategy that may increase decision on Murabahah financing in BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses quantitative research methods that are researches that use numbers ranging from data collection, interpretation to data, and appearance of results. Make an overview of the situation or event, explain relationships, test hypotheses, make predictions and get the meaning and implications of a problem that we want to solve. Simamora (2004), the population is a collection of all elements (units or individuals) of a kind that can be differentiated into the object of the research investigation. The population in this research is BPRS Trust Citizen Citizen Medan who submitted Murabahah financing of 168 customers. According to Sugiyono (2008), the sample is part of the number and characteristic of the population. Sample in this research is PT. BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan as many as 63 respondents. The sampling technique used the Slovin formula in Umar (2008). In this study will be used path analysis with the data obtained. The path Analysis method is also called path analysis method used to test the causal relationship between variables that have independent variables (exogenous) and dependent variables (endogenous).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Simultaneous Test (F-Test) (Direct Effect)

Table 1: ANOVA (F-Test) Direct Effect

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	554.958	7	79.280	15.515	.000 ^a
	Residual	291.257	57	5.110		
	Total	846.215	64			

Table 1 presents the F-count value is 15.515 with significance value (p-value) is equal to 0,000. When compared with F-table = 2.76 (for N = 65 or df = 58), it is known that F-count (15.515) > F-table (2.76) and sig-p (0,000) < 0,05, it can be concluded that seven independent variables (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence) simultaneously and significantly influence the dependent variable Y (Murabahah financing decision).

Partial Test (T-Test) (Direct Effect)

Table 2: Partial Test (T-Test) Direct Effect

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.285	3.547		.382	.719
	Product	.664	.245	.318	2.718	.009
	Price	.254	.112	.247	2.274	.027
	Place	.470	.161	.257	2.915	.005
	Promotion	.637	.172	.360	3.710	.000
	People	.329	.154	.207	2.134	.037
	Process	.304	.149	.197	2.038	.046
	Physical Evidence	.597	.280	.257	2.130	.037

Table 2 presents the value of the coefficient known that the probability value (significance) of each independent variable (marketing strategy) has a significance value is lower than 0.05. This work means that each marketing strategy variable has a significant effect on the decision to apply for Murabahah financing.

Coefficient of Determination

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.810 ^a	.656	.614	2.26048

Table 3 presents the results of Adjusted R which is 0.614 or 61.4%. The result shows that the research constructs contribute to explain Murabahah financing decision which is 61.4% while other factors outside of this study have influenced the remaining 38.6%.

Regression Equation (Direct Effect)

The regression equations are arranged according to the value of the calculation coefficient as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + b_7X_7 + e$$

$$Y = 1.285 + 0.664X_1 + 0.254X_2 + 0.470X_3 + 0.637X_4 + 0.329X_5 + 0.304X_6 + 597X_7 + e$$

The effect of interest on the decision to apply for Murabahah financing (Path analysis)

Table 4: The results of the second hypothesis test (Path Analysis)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.514	3.004		4.165	.000
	Minat Mengajukan	.559	.170	.384	3.297	.002

Table 4 presents that the t-value of interest = 3.297 with the value of significance = 0.002. Compared to the value of t-table and sig-value = 0.05, it can be concluded that the significance value of interest variables (0.002) < 0.05, it can be concluded that interest variables have a positive and significant influence on the decision to apply for Murabahah financing. Thus, H₀ is rejected, and H₁ accepted, the 2nd hypothesis states that interest has a significant effect on dependent variables Y (decision making Murabahah financing) is accepted.

The indirect effect of marketing strategy on the decision to apply for Murabahah financing

Table 5 The result of the third hypothesis t-test (indirect effect)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.596	3.481		.746	.459
	Product	.620	.237	.297	2.613	.011
	Price	.242	.108	.236	2.241	.029
	Place	.487	.156	.267	3.120	.003
	Promotion	.641	.166	.363	3.862	.000
	People	.468	.162	.294	2.891	.005
	Process	.544	.180	.353	3.014	.004
	Physical Evidence	.563	.272	.242	2.073	.043
	Minat Mengajukan	.374	.169	.257	2.218	.031

Table 5 presents the seven independent variables with interest as an intervening variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable Y (murabahah financing decision). It is indicated by significance value $X_1 = 0.011$, $X_2 = 0.029$, $X_3 = 0.003$, $X_4 = 0.000$, $X_5 = 0.005$, $X_6 = 0.004$, and $X_7 = 0.048$ while sig value of interest is 0.031 is lower than 0.05.

The value of the constant value of the influence of independent variables (the marketing strategy to the dependent variable Y (the decision to apply Murabahah financing) is 2,596. That is, compared with the first hypothesis constant value of 1.285, there is an increase in the constant value. High on the variable of the decision to propose Murabahah financing This proves that interest variables are proven as intervening variables that reinforce the relationship between the marketing strategy variables to the decision variables to apply for Murabaha financing The 3rd hypothesis that the interest is moderating or intervening the marketing strategy relationship with the decision financing of Murabahah, is acceptable.

Discussion

Based on the result of hypothesis testing 1, it is found that the influence of marketing strategy on the decision to apply Murabahah financing (direct influence). The results of this study are in line with Jesse Marcelina's research, Marketing Mix Effect (7p) on Purchase Decision at Guest House in Surabaya. The result of this research shows that the factors that influence the purchasing decision at the guest house in Surabaya are price factor, promotion, place, people and physical evidence that have positive and significant influence. From the quality of the answer to each questions item is related to 7 independent variables (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence) that F-value = 15.515 with significance value (p-value) = 0,000. When compared with F-table = 2.76 (for N = 65 or df = 58), it is known that F-count ($15.515 > 2.76$) and sig-p (0,000) < 0,05, so it can be concluded that 7 independent variables (product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence) simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable Y (Murabahah financing decision). Refers to the adjusted r-square value is 0.614. It means that the influence of independent variables on dependent variable Y (Murabahah financing proposal is $0.614 \times 100\% = 61.4\%$) Therefore, 61.4% of the decision variable for Murabahah financing can be explained by the marketing strategy variable. Furthermore, in the second hypothesis testing, the result of t-count interest value = 3.297 with significance value = 0.002. If compared to the t-table and sig-value 0.05, it can be concluded that the significance value of interest variables (0.002) < 0.05, so it can be concluded that interest variables have a positive

and significant influence on the decision to apply for Murabahah financing. H_0 was rejected, and H_1 was accepted, the 2nd hypothesis stating that interest had a significant effect on dependent variable Y (decision to apply for Murabahah financing), acceptable. On the third hypothesis testing, the result that the 7th independent variable with interest as intervening variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable Y (murabahah financing decision). It is indicated by the value of significance $X_1 = 0.011$, $X_2 = 0.029$, $X_3 = 0.003$, $X_4 = 0.000$, $X_5 = 0.005$, $X_6 = 0.004$, and $X_7 = 0.048$ while t-interest value is 0.031, all smaller than 0.05. Based on the result of the analysis with the coefficient value of each of the independent variables (product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence), it can be seen that the variables that influence the interest and decision to apply Murabahah financing are product variables (0.664) and promotion (0.637) while the variables that have low influence are price (0.254) and process (0.304). This work means that the strategy that needs to be improved to increase the interest and decision making of Murabahah financing further is to make pricing and marketing process improvements.

CONCLUSIONS & SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the result of research and discussion about the influence of marketing strategy to Murabahah cost decision with interest as an intervening variable, it can be concluded as follows the marketing strategy (product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence) has a significant influence on the Murabahah fee decision. The most influential variables on interest and decision to apply Murabahah financing are product variables (0.664). While the variables that have the lowest influence are price (0.254) and process (0.304). Strategies that need to improve further the decision to apply for Murabahah financing are to raise prices and marketing processes. Price Strategy is by adjusting or lowering prices with other competitors so that the volume of the decision of the submission of the loan can be further enhanced.

Strategic Process is by accelerating the process of financing filing and giving immediate answers to prospective customers so that the volume of murabahah financing decision increase.

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions obtained from this study, the author advised the following: to PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita Medan it is advisable to pay more attention to the aspect of price and process, where these two variables are the weakest factors affecting the decision to apply for Murabahah financing so that the decision to apply for Murabahah financing can be further enhanced in the future. It is hoped that product factors, promotions, and people especially employees who provide direct services to customers, may further improve the service so that the decision to apply for the Murabahah financing can be maximized. To other researchers, it is advisable to conduct similar research with a broader scale of research to enable a completely new research result.

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Cite this article:

Setiawan, A., Rini, E. S., Sadalia, I & Daulay, M. T. (2019) Analysis of Murabahah Financing Marketing Strategy at PT BPRS Amanah Insan Cita, Medan, North Sumatra, Indonesia. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(2), 64-73. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567414>

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